

Chemical Applications of X-ray Spectroscopy*

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The study of the X-ray absorption or X-ray emission spectrum of an atom in a molecule leads to important informations on the nature of chemical bonding (bonding sites, bond distance, bonding character, degree of covalency), valence state, coordination symmetry, and electronic structure of an atom in a molecule. The relation between the X-ray spectra and various solid state phenomena, such as valence state, bond distance, bonding character, and coordination symmetry are discussed. A number of examples have been presented to illustrate the various possibilities of the X-ray spectroscopy of the bonded atoms.

In recent years there has been considerable research interest in the influence of chemical bonding on the X-ray spectrum since the analysis of the fine features of the X-ray spectrum of the bonded atom provides a wealth of information regarding the valence state, oxidation-reduction phenomena, coordination, bonding, bond distance, and electronic structure of the atom under study. The X-ray spectroscopy has the advantage in characterising thin films and very small amount of poorly crystalline, glassy and liquid samples, and refractory materials which are difficult to characterise by conventional techniques (e.g., X-ray diffraction) or when the assignment of structure is not possible from magnetic measurements due to the inconclusive nature of the magnetic moment. The soft X-ray spectroscopy deals with the soft or low energy X-rays and is also known as low-energy X-ray spectroscopy. The basic principles of X-ray excitation for both the soft X-rays and more energetic or harder X-rays used in X-ray diffraction, are, however, the same.

In order to understand the origin of the X-ray spectrum of an atom let us consider the energy level diagram of aluminium presented in Fig. 1 in which the possible electron transitions have also been indicated. On absorption of X-rays, an electron is promoted from an inner level into an unoccupied level and the electron transitions from the K and $L_{2,3}$ levels to the valence electron levels lead to the X-ray K-absorption spectrum and the X-ray $L_{2,3}$ absorption spectrum, respectively. Since the valence electrons are involved in the formation of the chemical bonds, these X-ray absorption transitions are susceptible to significant changes when a change in chemical environment occurs. The X-ray absorption spectrum provides valuable information regarding the unoccupied part of the energy band system. On the other hand, the X-ray transitions occurring due to the electron transitions

Fig. 1. Energy level diagram with possible X-ray spectral transitions for aluminium.

from the valence electrons to the $L_{2,3}$ level or K level are designated as the X-ray emission bands and the resulting spectrum as the X-ray emission spectrum. The internal transitions from the $L_{2,3}$ shell to a vacancy created in the K shell are designated as the K_{α_1} and K_{α_2} emission lines. It is evident that the X-ray emission spectrum can provide valuable informations about the occupied part of the energy band system. The position, intensity, width and fine structure of the X-ray absorption and the X-ray emission spectra are characteristics of the bonded atoms and provide much valuable informations about the electronic structure of the materials. The applications of X-ray K-absorption spectroscopy in chemical bonding form the major part of this article. The electronic transitions occurring in the X-ray absorption spectroscopy are governed by the selection rule: $\Delta l = \pm 1$, where l is the orbital angular momentum quantum number. Thus, the transitions $1s \rightarrow 4p$, $1s \rightarrow 5p$, $2p \rightarrow 4d$ and $2p \rightarrow 5d$ are allowed transitions. On the other hand, the transition $1s \rightarrow 3d$ is a forbidden transition

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($\Delta l = \pm 2$). But due to the mixing of the s or d character with the p character by various mechanisms in transition metal compounds, the above selection rule is relaxed to some extent and the transitions $1s \rightarrow 3d$ and $1s \rightarrow 4s$ may become partially allowed.

Other than the above X-ray transitions, weaker emission lines are observed immediately to the high energy side of the K_{α_1} , K_{α_2} lines. These are known as satellites which are due to the doubly ionised atoms. These satellites arise from the $L_{\alpha_3} \rightarrow K$ transitions in presence of two simultaneous electron vacancies in the K and L shells. Although these satellites are quite weak in case of $3d$ transition metals, these lines are relatively intense in the elements of the third period of the Periodic Table and can be separated from the parent K_{α} line. Usually three satellites are observed and these are designated as $K_{\alpha'}$, $K_{\alpha''}$ and $K_{\alpha'''}$ lines. The influence of chemical bonding is also observed in these satellite lines. The energy shifts of the satellite lines occur towards the higher energy as the oxidation state of the metal ion increases. The $K_{\alpha_4}/K_{\alpha_3}$ intensity ratio increases from the lower oxidation state to the higher oxidation state. The more covalent is the bond, the lower is the $K_{\alpha_4}/K_{\alpha_3}$ intensity ratio and the lower is the energy position of the K_{α_3} and K_{α_4} satellite lines¹⁻⁵.

In the X-ray K-absorption spectroscopy the following regions are of interest to the chemists.

- Low energy region (0-20 eV),
- Energies up to 40 eV higher than the energy of the main absorption edge (Kossel fine structure),
- Energies in the region 40-150 eV,
- Energies beyond 150 eV (Kronig fine structure).

Applications of X-ray spectroscopy :

Nature of chemical bond : The X-ray spectroscopy is useful not only to find out the presence of a particular element but it can also give indication of how the bonded atom is combined chemically. The X-ray spectrum of the bonded atom is also useful to find out the metal-ligand chromophore system (MO_3N , MO_2N_2 , MN_2O_4 , MO_4N_2 etc), metal-ligand bond distance, and degree of covalency. A typical X-ray K-absorption spectrum of a compound is presented in Fig. 2 in which the absorption coefficient is plotted against energy in electron volt. In Fig. 2 there is an absorption maximum of low intensity (denoted by 'a') appearing at the low energy side of the main absorption edge. 'A' and 'B' denote the absorption maxima and α , β denote the absorption minima. 'A' represents the principal absorption maximum. The 'edge width' is defined as the energy difference between the principal

Fig. 2. X-Ray K-absorption spectrum* of $K_3[Co(SCN)_4(CN)_5]$, absorption maximum A and the first inflection point of the main absorption edge K (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. X-Ray K-absorption spectrum of N,N' -tetramethylenebis(salicylideneimine)cobalt(II).

The discipline of chemistry is one of the most beautifully balanced subjects with regard to the theory and experiment so that one can theoretically predict enough to make the subject interesting and yet there is sufficient scope for the experimental verification of the theoretical prediction. This is demonstrated below in few examples⁶ from the X-ray K-absorption spectra of metal-thiocyanato and metal-isothiocyanato bonded coordination compounds*.

The ambident nature of the thiocyanate ion is well known. Both sulphur and nitrogen atoms may be bonded to the metal resulting in $M-S$ or $M-N$ linkage. The molecular orbital energy level diagram

* The use of the term "complex" in coordination chemistry is confusing and should not be used. The suitable names have been suggested for the terms associated with the word "complex" e.g., coordination compound for complex compound, coordination titration for complexometric titration, etc.

of the thiocyanate ion^o is presented in Fig. 4. It is evident from the MO diagram that the lowest un-

Fig. 4. Molecular orbital energy level diagram of thiocyanate ion^o.

filled level is π_3 , a combination that is antibonding between the neighbouring atoms and is concentrated on the central atom. The highest filled level is π_3 which is a combination that is localised on the end atoms and is essentially non-bonding. In the coordination compounds of the thiocyanate ion the π_3 level is mainly localised on the sulphur atoms and the M-SCN bond is formed by the overlap of the metal orbitals with the π_2 orbital of thiocyanate ion. On the other hand, the M-NCS bond results from the overlap of the metal orbitals with the sp hybridized σ orbital of nitrogen. It is well known that SCN behaves as both π -donor and σ -donor but NCS acts as a σ -donor. In the thiocyanato-S coordination compounds the π_2 level acts as a π -donor and a vacancy is created in the π_2 level. On the absorption of X-rays, the ejected $1s$ electron would jump to the lowest energy empty π_2 level and this would lead to the observation of an X-ray K-absorption transition due to $1s \rightarrow \pi_2$ at low energy. But in the thiocyanato-N coordination compounds with M-NCS linkage, the π_2 level is primarily localised on the sulphur atom and the low energy $1s \rightarrow \pi_2$ transition is not expected to be observed. From the study of the X-ray K-absorption spectra of several thiocyanato coordination compounds, where the presence of M-SCN or M-NCS has been established firmly by other physico-chemical studies, we have shown that the above theoretical prediction is indeed correct^o. In the X-ray K-absorption spectra of the thiocyanato-S coordination compounds $K_2[Pt(SCN)_6]$, $K_2[Co(SCN)(CN)_5]$, and $trans-NH_4[Co(SCN)_2(DMGO)_2] \cdot 3H_2O$ (where DMGO = mono-anion of dimethylglyoxime), a low energy absorption maximum 'a' of medium intensity at around 7 eV (Figs. 5 and 6) appears and this indicates the presence of M-SCN bonding in these coordination compounds^o. On the other hand, in the X-ray K-absorption spectra of the thiocyanato-N coordination compounds $K_2[Co(NCS)_4] \cdot 4H_2O$, $K_2[Co(NCS)(CN)_5]$, and $[Fe(NCS)_2(py)_4]$ (where $py =$

Fig. 5. X-Ray K-absorption spectrum^o of (1) $K_2[Pt(SCN)_6]$, (2) $K_2[Co(NCS)_4] \cdot 4H_2O$, (3) $K_2[Co(NCS)(ON)_5]$, and (4) KSCN.

Fig. 6. X-Ray K-absorption spectrum^o of (1) $NH_4[Co(SON)_2(dimethylglyoxime)_2] \cdot 3H_2O$, (2) $[Co(thiocyanate)(PPh_3)(dimethylglyoxime)_2]$, and (3) $[Fe(NOS)_2(py)_4]$.

pyridine), no such low energy absorption maximum was observed^o in accordance with the above prediction. In the X-ray K-absorption spectrum (curve 2, Fig. 6) of $[Co(thiocyanate)(PPh_3)(DMGO)_2]$ which is a linkage isomeric mixture with the thiocyanato-S isomer being dominant, the intensity of the low energy absorption maximum is significantly lowered as both types of thiocyanato-S and thiocyanato-N isomers are present in the compound^o. Thus, the X-ray K-absorption spectroscopy is also useful to identify the presence of the mixture of linkage isomers in a coordination compound. In Fig. 5 (curve 4) the X-ray K-absorption spectrum of potassium thiocyanate which contains ionic thiocyanate, has also been included. The low energy absorption maximum 'a' is absent in the X-ray K-absorption spectrum of KSCN and a small increase in the value of the absorption coefficient was noticed in this low energy region. This is in line with the fact that the π_2 level in the thiocyanate ion is approximately divided between the sulphur and nitrogen

ends in the thiocyanate ion. The energy separations between the maxima $A-B=5$ eV, and $B-C=3$ eV correspond to $\pi_s-\sigma_s$ and $\sigma_s-\sigma_s$, respectively and are in accordance with the MO diagram depicted in Fig. 4.

The X-ray spectroscopy is useful to predict whether a chemical bond is covalent or ionic and the degree of covalency. We usually monitor the sharpness of the absorption maxima, edge shift of the principal absorption maximum, shift of the main absorption edge K, and the low energy peak for this purpose. Usually the ionic compounds exhibit sharp absorption maxima and the covalent compounds show somewhat broadened maxima. Accordingly, the cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate exhibits a sharp maximum due to the $1s \rightarrow 4p$ transition and N,N' -tetramethylenebis(salicylideneimine)cobalt(II) and N,N' -hexamethylenebis(salicylideneimine)cobalt(II) show broadened (split) absorption maximum⁷. The latter two compounds thus, exhibit covalent character and cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate shows ionic character. The shift of the principal K-absorption maximum to higher energy occurs if the compound is covalent. The energies of the principal absorption maximum (A) in several coordination compounds¹⁰ are in the order: $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+} < [\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+} < [\text{Cu}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ and this indicates the increasing covalent character of the compounds. The X-ray K-absorption studies of several coordination compounds with a variety of ligands have lead also to the serialisation of ligands in order of increasing covalency in agreement with the nephelauxetic series¹¹. The X-ray K-absorption measurements have been made to establish the relative covalent character of the M-S bond in coordination compounds. The main absorption edge shifts towards the high energy side and the shift decreases with the increase in covalency of the M-S bond. Thus, the bis(thiopropionic acid)copper(II) exhibits a larger shift ($\Delta=7.0$ eV) of the main absorption edge towards the higher energy in comparison to that of in bis(thiosalicylic acid)copper(II) ($\Delta=5.1$ eV), indicating that the Cu-S bond in the latter compound is more covalent¹². A larger edge width is the characteristic of the presence of a greater degree of covalency. The presence of a larger edge width (13.9 eV) in bis(thiosalicylic acid)lead(II) in comparison to the smaller edge width (12.6 eV) in bis(thiopropionic acid)lead(II) signifies the presence of a greater degree of covalency in Pb-S bond in the former compound¹³. The presence of the low energy absorption maximum is more prominent where the chemical bond is more covalent. The appearance of the low energy absorption maximum in $[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ and the absence of the low energy band in $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_2$ indicate the presence of a greater degree of covalency^{14,15} in $[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$.

Determination of valence state: The change in the valence state is associated with the change in the position of the principal absorption maximum (A) and the main absorption edge (K). The higher the oxidation state the greater are the shifts of the main

absorption edge and the principal absorption maximum towards higher energies. However, the relative energy of the principal absorption maximum is a more reliable criterion than the shift of the main absorption edge for the determination of the oxidation states of the metal ions¹⁶. The X-ray K-absorption data of the following compounds have been used to determine the valence state of cobalt:

Main absorption edge (K): Co^0 (metal), 0 eV $<$ Co^{II} - $\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 8 eV $<$ (acetylacetonato) N,N' -trimethylenebis(salicylideneimine)cobalt(III), 18 eV⁷.

Principal absorption maximum (A): Diaquo N,N' -trimethylenebis(salicylideneimine)cobalt(II), 17 eV $<$ (acetylacetonato) N,N' -trimethylenebis(salicylideneimine)cobalt(III), 32 eV⁷.

The assignments of the principal absorption maximum (A) in diaquo N,N' -trimethylenebis(salicylideneimine)cobalt(II) at 17 eV and in acetylacetonato N,N' -trimethylenebis(salicylideneimine)cobalt(III) at 32 eV to the $1s \rightarrow 4p$ and $1s \rightarrow 5p$ transitions, respectively are in accordance with the energy difference of the above transitions (17 eV and 30 eV)⁷.

The valence of sulphur in tetrasulphur tetranitride, S_4N_4 has been determined by the X-ray emission spectroscopy¹⁷. The molecule has a cage structure (Fig. 7) with a square set of nitrogen

Fig. 7. Structure of S_4N_4 (D_{2d} symmetry).

atoms and a bisphenoid of sulphur atoms¹⁸. The X-ray emission spectrum of the compound exhibits a K_α doublet and the position of the doublet identifies the sulphur atom in S_4N_4 to possess the oxidation state +3. This is in contrast to the expectations of the classical valence theory of sulphur having two oxidation states, viz. +2 and +4 in S_4N_4 . The X-ray spectroscopic data indicate that the electronic structure is a highly delocalised one and the electron distribution is evened out in the compound by delocalisation¹⁷. The S-S and S-N (linked by N) distances of 2.59 and 2.71 Å, respectively also indicate the presence of a significant S-S interaction and S-S bonding¹⁸.

The compounds or mixtures containing two oxidation states of a metal ion can also be characterised by the X-ray absorption and X-ray emission spectroscopy. The presence of the metal ion in two oxidation states has been found out from the observation of two distinct edges at different energies^{19,20}.

Determination of coordination stoichiometry : In coordination compounds of the ligands having many potential sites with different potential coordinating power, all the sites may not be utilised for coordination and this may lead to varied bonding which cannot sometimes be differentiated by the infrared spectroscopy due to the complexity of the infrared spectra arising out of the ligand absorptions. The X-ray K-absorption spectroscopy has been successfully applied for the determination of the coordination sites and for the differentiation of varied bonding. The X-ray K-absorption spectroscopy is specially useful for the determination of the coordination symmetry when the magnetic moment of the compound is inconclusive for the identification of the coordination symmetry. The spinel $\text{Co}[\text{Al}_2]\text{O}_4$ exhibits the room temperature magnetic moment of 4.9 B.M. and the assignment of the coordination symmetry unequivocally is not possible from the magnetic moment datum of the compound as the expected range of magnetic moments for the octahedral and tetrahedral cobalt(II) compounds are 4.7-5.2 and 4.4-4.8 B.M., respectively. But the X-ray K-absorption spectral data of the compound $\text{Co}[\text{Al}_2]\text{O}_4$ indicate unambiguously the presence of a tetrahedral symmetry²¹ in $\text{Co}[\text{Al}_2]\text{O}_4$. Usually the edge widths of the octahedral compounds are significantly lower than those of the tetrahedral compounds. In cobalt(II) compounds with the ligands containing oxygen donor sites, the edge width is usually in the range 5.0-7.6 eV for octahedral symmetry and 8.9-9.7 eV for tetrahedral symmetry.

The edge width can be calculated theoretically from the following equation¹⁸.

$$\text{Edge width} = \frac{k^2}{\sum |\chi_M - \chi_L|}$$

where k is a constant and has the values 7.7, 8.5, 16.4, 19.1 for cobalt, copper, zirconium and niobium, respectively; $\sum |\chi_M - \chi_L|$ is the sum of the metal atom and ligand atom electronegativity difference; χ_M is the Pauling electronegativity of the metal atom; and χ_L is the Pauling electronegativity of the ligand atom coordinated to the metal atom. A comparison of the observed and calculated edge widths of several compounds is presented in the Table 1 and the data show that it is possible to find out the coordination symmetry and metal-binding sites from the edge width studies.

Determination of the metal-ligand and metal-metal bond lengths :

The average radius (R) of the coordination sphere in the coordination compounds can be

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF THE CALCULATED AND OBSERVED VALUES OF THE EDGE WIDTHS OF VARIOUS COBALT(II) AND COPPER(II) COMPOUNDS

Compound	Coordination stoichiometry	$\sum \chi_M - \chi_L $	Edge width Observed (Calculated) eV	Ref.
$\text{Co}(\text{salsbn})^a$	CoN_2O_2	5.8	10.0 (10.2)	7
	CoN_4	4.8	10.0 (12.8)	
$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	CoO_6	10.2	5.6 (5.0)	7
$\text{Co}[\text{Al}_2]\text{O}_4$	CoO_4	6.8	8.9 (8.7)	21
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	CuO_6	9.6	7.6 (7.5)	13
$\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	CuO_6	8.0	8.4 (8.0)	22

^asalsbn = dianion of *N,N'*-tetramethylenebis(salicylideneimine).

calculated using the formula²³

$$R = \left(\frac{150}{\Delta E} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where ΔE is the energy separation between the absorption maximum (B) and minimum (β) (Fig. 3). Due to the effect of crystal field on the absorbing ions, the splitting of the bands in the region $B-\beta$ occurs and individual metal-ligand bond lengths can be calculated using the energy differences $B-\beta$, $B'-\beta$, $B-B'$ and $\beta'-\beta$. The metal-ligand bond length data presented in the Table 2 agree well with the bond length data obtained from the single crystal X-ray studies. Thus, the extended X-ray K-absorption fine structure analysis can be used as a supplement for X-ray diffraction method.

The splitting of the principal absorption maximum to two distinct maxima occurs due to the presence of unequal metal-ligand bond lengths. The observation of this splitting in both the magnetically dilute and magnetically concentrated coordination compounds indicates that it is not the characteristic of the presence of magnetic exchange interaction. However, the agreement of the $M-M$ data obtained from the X-ray K-absorption data and those of the X-ray diffraction data (Table 2) signifies the importance of the X-ray K-absorption spectroscopy in magnetochemistry. Although it is not possible to detect the presence of magnetic exchange from the room temperature magnetic moment data of copper(II) coordination compounds with normal magnetic moments, this can be detected by calculating the $\text{Cu}-\text{Cu}$ bond distance from the X-ray K-absorption data. The presence of ferromagnetism in Ni metal has also been detected by the X-ray K-absorption spectral studies¹⁷. The application of this methodology for the determination of the nature of bond and metal-ligand bond length in rubredoxin, an iron containing protein of bioinorganic interest has been demonstrated in Table 2.

The observation of fine structure (Fig. 3) on the high energy side of the X-ray K-absorption edge is

TABLE 2—VALUES OF METAL-LIGAND AND METAL-METAL BOND LENGTHS OF VARIOUS COBALT, COPPER AND IRON COMPOUNDS FROM X-RAY K-ABSORPTION SPECTROSCOPY AND SINGLE CRYSTAL X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA

Compound	ΔE eV	Bond length Å		Bond nature	Ref.
		X-Ray K-absorp- tion	X-Ray diffrac- tion		
Co metal	B- β =22	2.50	2.50	Co-Co	7
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	B- β =25	2.45		Co-O	7
Co(salbn) ^a	B- β =42	1.90		Co-O	7
Cu(hippuric acid) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	B- β =38.8	1.98	2.00	Cu-OH ₂	24
			1.92	Cu-OOO	
	B'- β =10.3	3.20	3.30	Cu-Cu	
Cu(aminobutyric acid) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	B- β =37.5	2.00	2.00	Cu-O	24
	B'- β =19.9	2.75	1.99	Cu-N	
Subredoxin		2.24	2.24	Fe-S	41

^aAbbreviation as in Table 1.

due to the scattering in the vicinity of the absorbing atom and the fine structure can be explained by considering the immediate environment surrounding the absorbing atom. The analyses of fine structure and edge width have made the X-ray K-absorption spectroscopy a potentially powerful tool for the determination of microscopic structure, metal-ligand and metal-metal bond lengths.

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of elements :

The X-ray spectroscopy can not only detect qualitatively the presence of the elements but it can also be used for the quantitative estimation of the elements. The beauty and power of the X-ray spectroscopy have been to detect and analyse very small quantities of elements²⁵, even upto 0.0001% and several elements can be quantitatively determined in alloys and minerals simultaneously. The X-ray spectroscopy has taken an important position as an instrumental method of analysis capable of precise, selective, and the most importantly non-destructive elemental determinations. It has led the field in taking the advantage of computers and mathematics for the rapid determination of spectral data and reduction of requirements for calibration of standards. In the usual chemical analyses of elements we usually determine the percentages of carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen, and leave the amount of oxygen which is often calculated by difference from 100%. The estimation of oxygen by the X-ray spectroscopy allows the elemental analysis upto 100% without going through the difference calculation for oxygen. Very small amount of samples can be analysed and the speed and precision of analysis by the X-ray spectroscopy are better than with the wet chemical techniques of analyses. The quantitative analyses of FeO in F₂O₃ and Al, Si, Mg in lunar rocks by the X-ray spectroscopy have been reported^{26,27}. The oxidation state of the elements are critical with the titrimetric or colorimetric determination, but not with the X-ray spectroscopic method. The presence of the mineral sinoite (silicon oxynitride) has been found out in a meteorite sample and the elements (Si, O and N) have been quantitatively determined²⁸. The detection of nitrogen in this sample indicates the presence

of nitrogen in the environment in which the mineral is formed²⁸ and illustrates the importance of the X-ray spectroscopic analysis. The X-ray spectroscopy has been successfully used for the analyses of air and water pollution, solid surfaces, catalysts, semiconductors, ores, slurry, cement, petroleum, coal, trace elements in medicine and biological fluids, and for the determination of the thickness of layer(s)²⁹⁻³³. The samples used for X-ray spectral measurements are non-destructive and may be brought to the court as evidence in prosecuting violators of pollution laws.

Analysis of man-made high-temperature plasma :

The distribution in man-made high-temperature plasmas has been found out by the X-ray spectroscopic analysis³⁴⁻⁴⁰.

In conclusion, we would like to indicate that the chemical applications of the X-ray spectroscopy are almost unlimited. Enough examples have been cited to unfold the power and beauty of the X-ray spectroscopy in solving the physico-chemical problems of interests to chemists. There is no doubt that the X-ray spectroscopy will continue to solve more problems related to the discipline of chemistry. The future promise of this methodology is bright and the X-ray spectroscopy will no doubt occupy an important place among the more powerful methods for the determination of structures of molecules and nature of chemical bond in materials.

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